

TRANSLATION OF THE VERBS "CRY" FROM UZBEK LANGUAGE INTO ENGLISH (BASED ON THE "STARRY NIGHTS" BY P.KADIROV)

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the analysis of verbs with the general meaning of “cry” that were used in both languages which are English and Uzbek. The novel itself was written in Uzbek language and translated into English and we will analyze the verbs in this article whether they have the full alternatives or not. The frequency of the verb usage and the translation transformations are analyzed and illustrated with the examples taken from the novel.

Key words: dominant verb, auxiliary verb, subordinate clause, simple clause, alternative, linguistic analysis;

O‘zbek tilidagi yig‘i fe’llarining ingliz tiliga tarjimasini (P.Qodirovning “Yulduzli tunlar” asari tadqiqi asosida)

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola o‘zbek tilida yozilgan “Yulduzli tunlar” romani ingliz tiliga o‘g‘irilganda har ikkala tilda ishlatilgan, to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri muqobil bo‘lgan yoki umuman muqobili bo‘lmagan “yig‘i” umumiy semali fe’llari tahliliga bag‘ishlangan. Unda fe’llarning qo‘llanilish chastotasi va tarjimadagi transformatsiyalari asardan olingan parcha hamda uning ingliz tilidagi tarjimasini yordamida tahlil qilinib, yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: dominant fe‘l, ko‘makchi fe‘l, ergash gap, sodda gap, muqobil, lingvistik tahlil.

It is not for nothing that we chose Pirmkul Kadyrov's novel "Starry nights" aiming the masterpieces of Uzbek literature. The purpose of this typological study is to analyze the translation and interpretation of the Uzbek verbs of cry in English and the problems in this process and the coordination of the translation between the two languages. The novel of our analyses has a serious of verbs used in sufficiently stylistically differentiated situations and it can be evaluated as an excellent linguistic material for theoretical-critical analysis. The novel is written in the language of a sharp literary story, details of real life (events of a dangerous historical period) are created on the basis of beautiful imagery and strong artistic influence. The ideas presented in are the selected lexical units and the literary load imposed on them is

great and unparalleled. The main characters in the work are the descendants of Umarshaikh Mirza, who are depicted in the novel as possessors of high thinking and insight, every mental and emotional situation in them is skillfully shown by P.Kadirov with the help of verbs of crying and through them the relationship of the heroes to the historical events of that time. This given work of the writer requires approaching the construction of the plot of the work with deep observation and a high linguistic knowledge level.

Thinking about the verbs of crying used in the text of the novel, the usual (dominant) verbs are used several times and at the same time, since this work is a historical novel, the verbs of crying in the archaic form and the theme of "crying" are from one and several words. We have come across the cases where it is used by means of word combinations. In some places, we witness the purposeful use of synonymous and anonymous and repeated components in one sentence. At the same time, during the analysis, it is possible to obtain complete linguistic information not only by means of collective verbs but also by means of general verbs.

The novel "Starry nights" was written by Pirimkul Kadirov in Uzbek and since it is dedicated to historical events and the life of historical figures, the set of words used in it was given artistic coloring with the help of several different phonetic means. Although the degree of alternation of verbs in the English and Uzbek languages, which are not related to each other, is at an advanced level, as a result of the differences in cultures and the unrepeatable stylistic skills of the translator, the verbs that are alternate in the dictionaries of both languages create incompatibilities in the translated text. This situation creates the need for appropriate use of linguistic translation transformations at different levels of the language in the process. Before that, we will express the frequency of use of verbs with the general meaning "cry" in the literary text that is the focus of our analysis through a table (based on the 304-page version of the work in Uzbek):

Table 1.

1	Yig'lamoq	34
2	Ko'zidan yosh oqmoq/tommoq/ /sirg'almoq/to'kilmoq/chiqmoq quyilmoq	16
3	Ko'ziga yosh olmoq/kelmoq	13
4	Ko'zi yoshlanmoq/yoshga to'lmoq	12
5	Yig'lab yubormoq/boshlamoq	9
6	O'pkasi to'lmoq	6
7	Dodlamoq/Dod solmoq	5
8	Yig'lamsiramoq	4
9	Ko'zida yosh yiltillamoq	4
10	O'zini yig'idan tutolmaslik	3

(Other verbs with cry sign found in the work, but not reflected in table, are used in indicator below 3). The verb to cry is the dominant lexicon in the Uzbek language "lexical-semantic field of common verbs of cry", as in the lexicon of the verb "yig'i" in English. It is precisely for this reason that it has gained the main advantage in terms of frequency of use in the work of art. But it is important that the thirty four occurrences of this verb in the work of art are used in different situations and meanings. Let's analyze in detail:

In the text, the verb "to cry" is used in eight places in the sense of doing something while crying as *yig'lab gapirmoq*, *yig'lab iltimos qilmoq*, *yig'lab iltijo qilmoq*, *yig'lab minnatdorchilik bildirmoq*.and other similar meanings. In the following example, the structure of the part of the sentence has undergone a lexical transformation in the translation and has been replaced by a one-component lexical unit, which is called the participle form in English.

Xonzoda begim so'nggi so'zlarini *yig'lab aytdi-yu*, otini qamchilab, ark darvozasiga qarab intildi. [1:77]

Khanzoda-begim *pronounced* the last words *sobbing*. She stabbed the horse and rushed to the gate of the ark. [2:119]

In this sentence, the verb to cry as part of the Uzbek adverb clause is translated by means of separate independent verbs cry and ask in the English equivalent clause:

Hozir pulga oshliq topilmaydi. Bolalarim, «non» *deb yig'lab*, har kuni yurak-bag'rimizni ezurlar. Agar iloji bo'lsa, ozgina un...[1:89]

“Nowadays it’s impossible to buy food, and children *cry* every day and *ask for* bread, my heart is tearing apart. If it’s possible, just some flour...”[2:91]

In the case of the next use of the verb to cry in Uzbek what is the case of begging. How to speak as an answer to such questions, expressing the manner of execution of an action or situation, acting as a subjunctive of a subordinate part of a compound sentence [3:294]. In its translation into English, due to the fact that the two languages are unrelated languages and the linguistic features of the English language, the two component complex verb is translated as a one component complex verb. This is an independent verb:

U tizzasi bilan yurib Boburga yaqinlashar ekan, *yig'lab iltijo qildi*. [1:117]

He crept up on his knees closer to Babur, and *burst out sobbing*. [2:98]

In the following example, the complex subordinate component verb combination yelled and cried is translated into English by means of a single component, separate and independent verb. So, what did this verb do in the linguistic analysis of the sentence?

Bobur hamma bek va navkarlari bilan kelayotganini ko'rgan Tohir otdan o'zini yerga tashlab, *dod solib yig'lab gapirdi*: — Nechun Samarqandni tashlab keldingiz, amirzodam?! [1:225]

“Why did you leave Samarqand, my master?!” – Tokhir *yelled and cried*. [2:176]

In some places, to avoid literal translation and to focus on conveying the meaning to the reader in a more complete and at the same time more affective way, sentences are generally translated into other words. In this case, a grammatical change occurred between word groups-sentence fragments:

Darvesh govning yig‘lab gapirgan so‘zlari go‘yo uzoqdan eshitildi.

The entreaties of dervish Gov were drowning in these cries.

In the example below, the verb to cry comes in the adverbial case and in what state and in what way? There will be an answer to this questions. In english, the part of the sentence performed by the verb under analysis is the same as the interrogative, but the noun is the first form of the adjective in this language (crying).

To sum up, each language has its own unique system and lexical units. Doing a comparative analysis of two or more languages from the perspective of literary translation, there no doubt that their similarities and differences will emerge. And these create an absolute alternative or incapability in the translation. Not any dictionary, whether electronic or in book form, can convey these aspects in a way that a skilled translator understands and make the reader understand thoroughly. Therefore, it would be appropriate to pay more attention to the field of translation in our country and increase the position of the human factor in it.

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